

Appendices

(for the paper entitled: “**How Cultural Background and Cognitive Style Shape Responses to Sustainability-Aware Explanations in Healthy Food Recommender Systems**”)

Appendix 1 - Cognitive Style Question Groups

Group 1: Personal Influence (short form: **PI**)

Variable name	Statement
PI_1	I would rather depend on myself than others.
PI_2	I rely on myself most of the time; I rarely rely on others.
PI_3	I often do my own thing.
PI_4	My personal identity, independent of others, is very important to me.

Group 2: Performance and Achievement (short form: **PA**)

Variable name	Statement
PA_1	It is important that I perform better than others.
PA_2	Winning is very important to me.
PA_3	Competition is a natural part of life.
PA_4	When another person performs better than I do, I feel tense.

Group 3: Cooperation and Social Relationships (short form: **CSR**)

Variable name	Statement
CSR_1	If someone I work or study with receives recognition, I feel proud.
CSR_2	The well-being of people around me is important to me.
CSR_3	Spending time with others is enjoyable to me.
CSR_4	I feel good when I cooperate with others.

Group 4: Family Responsibilities and Obligations (short form: **FRO**)

Variable name	Statement
FRO_1	Parents and children should stay together as much as possible.
FRO_2	I feel a duty to take care of my family even if it requires sacrifice.
FRO_3	Family members should support each other even if it requires personal sacrifice.
FRO_4	I would give up an activity I enjoy if my family did not approve of it.

Group 5: Processing Information and Making Decisions (short form: **PIMD**)

Variable name	Statement
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PIMD_1	I focus on specific details when making decisions.
PIMD_2	I consider the broader context when making decisions.
PIMD_3	I prefer clear rules and structured information.
PIMD_4	I think about how different factors are interconnected.

Appendix 2 - Weight Assignments for Formula (10) about Recipe Score:

The weights are heuristically assigned based on the objectives of each recommendation task rather than learned from historical interaction data. For example, the *Quick & Healthy* choice task assigns slightly higher weights to health and preparation-time-related features because users are expected to prioritize convenience while still maintaining healthy eating. In contrast, the *Environmentally Friendly Choice* task assigns stronger importance to sustainability-related features in order to explicitly promote environmentally responsible food decisions. The weighting strategy therefore enables the recommender to adapt recommendation behavior according to the contextual goals of different food-decision scenarios while maintaining a balance between personalization, health, and sustainability.

Task	w_p (preference)	w_h (health)	w_s (sustainability)	w_t (task)	Σ
Quick & Healthy	0.25	0.30	0.20	0.25	1.00
Everyday Healthy	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	1.00
Environmentally Friendly	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	1.00

Notes:

- **t2 and t3 use a flat 0.25 split.** All four components contribute equally; the task-specific bias lives entirely inside the Task feature sub-score, not in the outer weights.
- **t1 tilts toward health (0.30) at the expense of sustainability (0.20).** This prevents “quick” from drifting into junk food, since the TaskFeature term for the quick scenario rewards only short prep time.
- **Preference is held constant at 0.25 across all tasks.** Users feel that their stated profile matters equally regardless of scenario.

Task feature sub-score

The Task feature term re-injects the task dimension into the score with its own internal weighting:

- **Quick and healthy task:** $1 - \text{normalize}(\text{prep_time})$
- **Everyday_healthy task:** $0.30 \cdot \text{health} + 0.30 \cdot \text{protein} + 0.20 \cdot (1 - \text{calories}) + 0.20 \cdot (1 - \text{sodium})$
- **Environmentally friendly task:** $0.50 \cdot \text{protein_source_score} + 0.50 \cdot \text{sustainability}$

Consequence: health and sustainability are effectively double-counted in the everyday_healthy and eco_friendly scenarios — once via w_h or w_s on the normalized raw scores, and again inside TaskFeature weighted by w_t.

Appendix 3 - Demographic information of the participants

Cultural background	Region	Nationality	n	
Asian	Eastern Asia	China	5	2,564%
		Japan	1	
		South Korea	1	
	South Eastern Asia	Vietnam	47	17,216%
	Southern Asia	Bangladesh	31	19,414%
		India	8	
		Pakistan	8	
Sri Lanka		6		
European	Eastern Europe	Hungary	3	3,663%
		Ukraine	3	
		Romania	2	
		Czechia	1	
		Russia	1	
	Southern Europe	Bosnia and Herzegovina	9	6,960%
		Serbia	3	
		Slovenia	3	
		Italy	2	
		Croatia	1	
		Spain	1	
	Western Europe	Austria	93	37,729%
		Germany	8	
		France	1	
Luxembourg		1		
Other	Middle Eastern	Iran	12	12,454%
	South America	Mexico	3	
	North America	USA	5	
	Africa	Nigeria	3	
	Mixed	Turkey	3	
	Other		8	

Appendix 4 - RQ1: Effects of Cultural Background and Cognitive Style on Behavioural Choice

4.1 Descriptive outcomes by culture

group	n_participants	n_decisions	chose_recommended_pct	picked_healthiest_pct	picked_most_sustainable_pct	chosen_health_score_mean	chosen_health_score_sd	chosen_sustainability_score_mean	chosen_sustainability_score_sd
Asian	107	321	46.1	36.4	68.2	68.82	9.42	91.83	9.14
European	132	396	34.6	34.8	59.3	71.11	12.47	87.77	13.47

4.2 Block Wald tests (culture + cognitive-style blocks)

outcome	family	n_dec	n_pp	grp_chi2	grp_df	grp_p	cog_chi2	cog_df	cog_p	ok	grp_p_fdr	cog_p_fdr
chose_recommended	GEE-logit	717	239	5.22	1	0.0223	8.484	5	0.1315	True	0.0372	0.6574
picked_healthiest	GEE-logit	717	239	0.01	1	0.9199	2.793	5	0.7318	True	0.9199	0.9148
picked_most_sustainable	GEE-logit	717	239	3.807	1	0.0510	3.812	5	0.5767	True	0.0638	0.9148
chosen_health_score	LMM (random intercept)	717	239	6.885	1	0.0087	3.299	5	0.6540	True	0.0217	0.9148
chosen_sustainability_score	LMM (random intercept)	717	239	16.44	1	5.023e-05	1.024	5	0.9606	True	0.0003	0.9606

4.3 Kruskal-Wallis (robustness)

outcome	n_decisions	n_groups	H	df	p	eta_sq	p_fdr
chose_recommended	717	2	9.793	1	0.0018	0.012	0.0044
picked_healthiest	717	2	0.198	1	0.6565	-0.001	0.6565
picked_most_sustainable	717	2	6.012	1	0.0142	0.007	0.0237
chosen_health_score	717	2	5.09	1	0.0241	0.006	0.0301
chosen_sustainability_score	717	2	12.03	1	0.0005	0.015	0.0026

4.4 Cognitive-style analysis (Asian vs European)

Mean (SD) of each cognitive dimension per cultural group (one row per participant, scores are dataset units).

group	n	personal_influence_mean	personal_influence_sd	performance_achievement_mean	performance_achievement_sd	cooperation_relationships_mean	cooperation_relationships_sd	family_responsibility_mean	family_responsibility_sd	processing_decisions_mean	processing_decisions_sd
Asian	107	4.12	0.79	3.54	0.92	4.08	0.84	3.92	0.92	4.14	0.78
European	132	3.8	0.76	3.02	0.95	3.91	0.76	3.12	0.86	4	0.68

Per-dimension coefficients extracted from the 5 outcome models (binary outcomes report log-odds; continuous outcomes report raw units).

outcome	cognitive_dim	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high	odds_ratio
chose_recommended	personal_influence	0.0758	0.1133	0.5036	-0.1463	0.2979	1.079
chose_recommended	performance_achievement	-0.1042	0.0835	0.2116	-0.2678	0.0593	0.901
chose_recommended	cooperation_relationships	0.1338	0.1141	0.2412	-0.0899	0.3575	1.143
chose_recommended	family_responsibility	0.0997	0.1004	0.3206	-0.0971	0.2966	1.105
chose_recommended	processing_decisions	0.0796	0.1333	0.5504	-0.1817	0.341	1.083
picked_healthiest	personal_influence	-0.126	0.124	0.3097	-0.3691	0.1171	0.882
picked_healthiest	performance_achievement	-0.0398	0.0902	0.6592	-0.2165	0.137	0.961
picked_healthiest	cooperation_relationships	0.0018	0.1142	0.9874	-0.222	0.2256	1.002
picked_healthiest	family_responsibility	0.1376	0.1063	0.1956	-0.0708	0.3459	1.148
picked_healthiest	processing_decisions	-0.0106	0.1309	0.9356	-0.2671	0.246	0.989
picked_most_sustainable	personal_influence	0.1907	0.1302	0.1432	-0.0646	0.4459	1.21
picked_most_sustainable	performance_achievement	0.001	0.1019	0.9921	-0.1987	0.2007	1.001
picked_most_sustainable	cooperation_relationships	0.0506	0.1217	0.6776	-0.188	0.2892	1.052
picked_most_sustainable	family_responsibility	0.0565	0.1039	0.5866	-0.1471	0.2601	1.058

picked_most_sustainable	processing_decisions	-0.1428	0.1385	0.3025	-0.4141	0.1286	0.867
chosen_health_score	personal_influence	-0.6358	0.6286	0.3118	-1.868	0.5963	
chosen_health_score	performance_achievement	-0.217	0.4891	0.6573	-1.176	0.7415	
chosen_health_score	cooperation_relationships	0.3145	0.5959	0.5977	-0.8535	1.482	
chosen_health_score	family_responsibility	0.5872	0.5352	0.2726	-0.4618	1.636	
chosen_health_score	processing_decisions	0.1585	0.7031	0.8216	-1.22	1.536	
chosen_sustainability_score	personal_influence	0.3925	0.6575	0.5505	-0.896	1.681	
chosen_sustainability_score	performance_achievement	0.0566	0.5115	0.9119	-0.9459	1.059	
chosen_sustainability_score	cooperation_relationships	0.5016	0.6233	0.4210	-0.72	1.723	
chosen_sustainability_score	family_responsibility	-0.1823	0.5598	0.7447	-1.28	0.9149	
chosen_sustainability_score	processing_decisions	-0.2763	0.7353	0.7071	-1.718	1.165	

Spearman correlations (decision-level) between each cognitive score and each behavioural outcome; FDR-adjusted across the 25 tests.

outcome	cognitive_dim	n	spearman_rho	p	p_fdr
chose_recommended	personal_influence	717	0.053	0.1528	0.4195
chose_recommended	performance_achievement	717	0.014	0.7007	0.8759
chose_recommended	cooperation_relationships	717	0.107	0.0040	0.0715
chose_recommended	family_responsibility	717	0.103	0.0057	0.0715
chose_recommended	processing_decisions	717	0.058	0.1212	0.4195
picked_healthiest	personal_influence	717	-0.027	0.4754	0.7428
picked_healthiest	performance_achievement	717	-0.015	0.6802	0.8759
picked_healthiest	cooperation_relationships	717	0.011	0.7712	0.9181
picked_healthiest	family_responsibility	717	0.052	0.1678	0.4195
picked_healthiest	processing_decisions	717	-0.022	0.5482	0.7614
picked_most_sustainable	personal_influence	717	0.069	0.0667	0.3335
picked_most_sustainable	performance_achievement	717	0.036	0.3341	0.5568
picked_most_sustainable	cooperation_relationships	717	0.025	0.5088	0.7482
picked_most_sustainable	family_responsibility	717	0.07	0.0622	0.3335
picked_most_sustainable	processing_decisions	717	0.002	0.9599	0.9599
chosen_health_score	personal_influence	717	-0.046	0.2216	0.4616
chosen_health_score	performance_achievement	717	-0.055	0.1421	0.4195
chosen_health_score	cooperation_relationships	717	-0.006	0.8757	0.9519
chosen_health_score	family_responsibility	717	0.003	0.9319	0.9599
chosen_health_score	processing_decisions	717	-0.046	0.2149	0.4616
chosen_sustainability_score	personal_influence	717	0.06	0.1070	0.4195
chosen_sustainability_score	performance_achievement	717	0.04	0.2797	0.5378
chosen_sustainability_score	cooperation_relationships	717	0.037	0.3197	0.5568
chosen_sustainability_score	family_responsibility	717	0.083	0.0271	0.2255
chosen_sustainability_score	processing_decisions	717	0.007	0.8424	0.9519

4.5 Full coefficient tables

Outcome: chose_recommended

Family: GEE-logit • n = 717 decisions (239 participants)

Formula: chose_recommended ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high	odds_ratio	or_ci_low	or_ci_high
Intercept	-1.317	0.5763	0.0223	-2.446	-0.1872	0.268	0.087	0.829
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-0.4078	0.1785	0.0223	-0.7576	-0.058	0.665	0.469	0.944
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	0.2712	0.1994	0.1738	-0.1196	0.6621	1.312	0.887	1.939
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.0476	0.2	0.8121	-0.4396	0.3445	0.954	0.644	1.411
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_health]	-0.252	0.1919	0.1891	-0.6281	0.1241	0.777	0.534	1.132
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	-0.1245	0.1922	0.5174	-0.5013	0.2523	0.883	0.606	1.287
personal_influence	0.0758	0.1133	0.5036	-0.1463	0.2979	1.079	0.864	1.347
performance_achievement	-0.1042	0.0835	0.2116	-0.2678	0.0593	0.901	0.765	1.061
cooperation_relationships	0.1338	0.1141	0.2412	-0.0899	0.3575	1.143	0.914	1.43
family_responsibility	0.0997	0.1004	0.3206	-0.0971	0.2966	1.105	0.907	1.345
processing_decisions	0.0796	0.1333	0.5504	-0.1817	0.341	1.083	0.834	1.406

Outcome: picked_healthiest

Family: GEE-logit • n = 717 decisions (239 participants)

Formula: picked_healthiest ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high	odds_ratio	or_ci_low	or_ci_high
Intercept	-0.5076	0.6499	0.4348	-1.782	0.7662	0.602	0.168	2.152

C(culture_group)[T.European]	-0.0177	0.1765	0.9199	-0.3637	0.3282	0.982	0.695	1.388
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	-0.2247	0.2071	0.2780	-0.6306	0.1813	0.799	0.532	1.199
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.0313	0.1991	0.8750	-0.4216	0.359	0.969	0.656	1.432
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_health]	0.456	0.1785	0.0106	0.1061	0.8059	1.578	1.112	2.239
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	0.0961	0.2024	0.6350	-0.3006	0.4928	1.101	0.74	1.637
personal_influence	-0.126	0.124	0.3097	-0.3691	0.1171	0.882	0.691	1.124
performance_achievement	-0.0398	0.0902	0.6592	-0.2165	0.137	0.961	0.805	1.147
cooperation_relationships	0.0018	0.1142	0.9874	-0.222	0.2256	1.002	0.801	1.253
family_responsibility	0.1376	0.1063	0.1956	-0.0708	0.3459	1.148	0.932	1.413
processing_decisions	-0.0106	0.1309	0.9356	-0.2671	0.246	0.989	0.766	1.279

Outcome: picked_most_sustainable

Family: GEE-logit • n = 717 decisions (239 participants)

Formula: picked_most_sustainable ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high	odds_ratio	or_ci_low	or_ci_high
Intercept	1.103	0.6659	0.0976	-0.2019	2.409	3.014	0.817	11.12
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-0.3539	0.1814	0.0510	-0.7093	0.0016	0.702	0.492	1.002
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	0.0555	0.216	0.7971	-0.3679	0.479	1.057	0.692	1.614
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	0.0378	0.2049	0.8536	-0.3638	0.4394	1.039	0.695	1.552
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_health]	-0.7158	0.22	0.0011	-1.147	-0.2846	0.489	0.318	0.752
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	-1.935	0.2162	3.491e-19	-2.359	-1.511	0.144	0.095	0.221
personal_influence	0.1907	0.1302	0.1432	-0.0646	0.4459	1.21	0.937	1.562

performance_achievement	0.001	0.1019	0.9921	-0.1987	0.2007	1.001	0.82	1.222
cooperation_relationships	0.0506	0.1217	0.6776	-0.188	0.2892	1.052	0.829	1.335
family_responsibility	0.0565	0.1039	0.5866	-0.1471	0.2601	1.058	0.863	1.297
processing_decisions	-0.1428	0.1385	0.3025	-0.4141	0.1286	0.867	0.661	1.137

Outcome: chosen_health_score

Family: LMM (random intercept) • n = 717 decisions (239 participants)

Formula: chosen_health_score ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	65.84	3.358	1.364e-85	59.26	72.42
C(culture_group)[T.European]	2.483	0.9464	0.0087	0.6283	4.338
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	0.396	1.05	0.7062	-1.663	2.455
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	1.376	1.046	0.1884	-0.6744	3.427
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	3.012	1.02	0.0032	1.012	5.011
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	1.701	1.02	0.0953	-0.298	3.7
personal_influence	-0.6358	0.6286	0.3118	-1.868	0.5963
performance_achievement	-0.217	0.4891	0.6573	-1.176	0.7415
cooperation_relationships	0.3145	0.5959	0.5977	-0.8535	1.482
family_responsibility	0.5872	0.5352	0.2726	-0.4618	1.636
processing_decisions	0.1585	0.7031	0.8216	-1.22	1.536
Group Var	0.0027	0.0382	0.9446	-0.0721	0.0774

Outcome: chosen_sustainability_score

Family: LMM (random intercept) • n = 717 decisions (239 participants)

Formula: chosen_sustainability_score ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	91.79	3.512	1.344e-150	84.9	98.67
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-4.013	0.9898	5.023e-05	-5.953	-2.073
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	1.453	1.099	0.1861	-0.7007	3.606
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.8416	1.094	0.4418	-2.986	1.303
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	-2.372	1.061	0.0254	-4.452	-0.2928
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	-4.151	1.061	9.161e-05	-6.23	-2.071
personal_influence	0.3925	0.6575	0.5505	-0.896	1.681
performance_achievement	0.0566	0.5115	0.9119	-0.9459	1.059
cooperation_relationships	0.5016	0.6233	0.4210	-0.72	1.723
family_responsibility	-0.1823	0.5598	0.7447	-1.28	0.9149
processing_decisions	-0.2763	0.7353	0.7071	-1.718	1.165
Group Var	0.0063	0.0386	0.8695	-0.0693	0.0819

Appendix 5 - RQ2: Cultural Background & Cognitive Style → Evaluations of Sustainability-Aware Explanations

5.1 Descriptive ratings by group (mean, SD per dimension)

group	n	n_r	transpar	transpare	trust	trust	satisfac	satisfac	persuasi	persuasive	effectiv	effectiv	efficiency	efficiency	understand	understand	manipulation	manipulation
			enc	ncy	mean	sd	tion	tion	ven	ness	ness	ness	ness	ness	ability	ability	mean	sd
Asian	107	321	3.95	0.98	3.86	1.08	3.84	1.05	3.94	1.01	3.87	1.04	3.87	1.05	3.87	0.99	3.19	1.36
European	132	396	3.26	1.18	2.64	1.17	2.8	1.18	3.04	1.2	2.62	1.25	2.59	1.28	3.01	1.15	1.86	1.14

5.2 Block Wald tests (grouping factor + cognitive style)

outcome	n_ratings	n_p	grp_chi2	grp_df	grp_p	cog_chi2	cog_df	cog_p	ok	grp_p_fdr	cog_p_fdr
transparency	717	239	12.84	1	0.0003	31.06	5	9.100e-06	True	0.0003	1.456e-05
trust	717	239	51.06	1	8.959e-13	47.96	5	3.615e-09	True	2.389e-12	1.446e-08
satisfaction	717	239	35.87	1	2.112e-09	41.19	5	8.604e-08	True	3.379e-09	2.294e-07
persuasiveness	717	239	25.67	1	4.049e-07	53.85	5	2.250e-10	True	4.847e-07	1.800e-09
effectiveness	717	239	50.22	1	1.378e-12	39.23	5	2.139e-07	True	2.755e-12	4.278e-07
efficiency	717	239	55.13	1	1.129e-13	28.24	5	3.262e-05	True	8.590e-13	3.728e-05
understandability	717	239	25.58	1	4.241e-07	29.62	5	1.753e-05	True	4.847e-07	2.337e-05
manipulation	717	239	53.87	1	2.147e-13	18.42	5	0.0025	True	8.590e-13	0.0025

5.3 Kruskal-Wallis (robustness)

outcome	n_ratings	n_groups	H	df	p	eta_sq	p_fdr
transparency	717	2	65.56	1	5.632e-16	0.09	5.632e-16
trust	717	2	165.4	1	7.348e-38	0.23	5.879e-37
satisfaction	717	2	129.9	1	4.417e-30	0.18	7.067e-30
persuasiveness	717	2	100.5	1	1.162e-23	0.139	1.550e-23
effectiveness	717	2	161.8	1	4.545e-37	0.225	1.330e-36
efficiency	717	2	161.6	1	4.987e-37	0.225	1.330e-36
understandability	717	2	98.08	1	4.010e-23	0.136	4.582e-23
manipulation	717	2	157.4	1	4.244e-36	0.219	8.488e-36

5.4 Full LMM coefficient tables

Dimension: transparency

LMM (random intercept) — n = 717 ratings (239 participants)

Formula: transparency ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	1.548	0.4602	0.0008	0.6455	2.45
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-0.4705	0.1313	0.0003	-0.728	-0.2131
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	0.0778	0.1458	0.5936	-0.2079	0.3635
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.0955	0.1452	0.5106	-0.3801	0.189
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	0	0.0629	1.0000	-0.1233	0.1233
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	0.0795	0.0629	0.2062	-0.0438	0.2028
personal_influence	0.0335	0.0872	0.7007	-0.1375	0.2045
performance_achievement	0.1048	0.0679	0.1224	-0.0282	0.2379
cooperation_relationships	0.2044	0.0827	0.0134	0.0423	0.3665
family_responsibility	0.1333	0.0743	0.0726	-0.0122	0.2789
processing_decisions	0.1243	0.0976	0.2025	-0.0669	0.3156
Group Var	1.369	0.1933	1.430e-12	0.99	1.748

Dimension: trust

LMM (random intercept) — n = 717 ratings (239 participants)

Formula: trust ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	0.9196	0.4619	0.0465	0.0142	1.825
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-0.9418	0.1318	8.959e-13	-1.2	-0.6835
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	0.0789	0.1463	0.5896	-0.2078	0.3657
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.0395	0.1457	0.7864	-0.3251	0.2461
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	0.0544	0.0645	0.3987	-0.0719	0.1807
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	0.0335	0.0645	0.6035	-0.0929	0.1598
personal_influence	0.0074	0.0875	0.9329	-0.1642	0.179
performance_achievement	0.1134	0.0681	0.0958	-0.0201	0.2469
cooperation_relationships	0.2575	0.083	0.0019	0.0949	0.4202
family_responsibility	0.1829	0.0745	0.0142	0.0368	0.329
processing_decisions	0.1688	0.0979	0.0847	-0.0231	0.3607
Group Var	1.299	0.1854	2.428e-12	0.9356	1.662

Dimension: satisfaction

LMM (random intercept) — n = 717 ratings (239 participants)

Formula: satisfaction ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	1.176	0.4646	0.0114	0.2655	2.087
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-0.7939	0.1326	2.112e-09	-1.054	-0.5341
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	0.0379	0.1471	0.7965	-0.2505	0.3263
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.0828	0.1465	0.5722	-0.37	0.2045
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	0.0502	0.0644	0.4358	-0.0761	0.1765

C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	0.1255	0.0644	0.0514	-0.0007	0.2518
personal_influence	-0.0126	0.0881	0.8861	-0.1852	0.16
performance_achievement	0.0555	0.0685	0.4181	-0.0788	0.1897
cooperation_relationships	0.2112	0.0835	0.0114	0.0476	0.3748
family_responsibility	0.2035	0.075	0.0066	0.0565	0.3504
processing_decisions	0.1974	0.0985	0.0451	0.0043	0.3904
Group Var	1.319	0.1877	2.072e-12	0.9514	1.687

Dimension: persuasiveness

LMM (random intercept) — n = 717 ratings (239 participants)

Formula: persuasiveness ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	1.146	0.434	0.0083	0.2953	1.996
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-0.6266	0.1237	4.049e-07	-0.869	-0.3842
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	0.0615	0.1373	0.6542	-0.2076	0.3305
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.0682	0.1367	0.6179	-0.3362	0.1998
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	-0.0586	0.0713	0.4114	-0.1983	0.0812
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	0.0167	0.0713	0.8144	-0.123	0.1565
personal_influence	-0.0331	0.0821	0.6872	-0.1941	0.1279
performance_achievement	0.1077	0.0639	0.0920	-0.0176	0.233
cooperation_relationships	0.2005	0.0779	0.0100	0.0478	0.3531
family_responsibility	0.204	0.0699	0.0035	0.0669	0.3411
processing_decisions	0.2299	0.0919	0.0124	0.0498	0.4099
Group Var	0.8406	0.1333	2.879e-10	0.5793	1.102

Dimension: effectiveness

LMM (random intercept) — n = 717 ratings (239 participants)

Formula: effectiveness ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	1.388	0.4699	0.0031	0.4669	2.309
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-0.9494	0.134	1.378e-12	-1.212	-0.6868
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	-0.0286	0.1487	0.8474	-0.3201	0.2629
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.0816	0.1481	0.5819	-0.3719	0.2087
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	-0.0335	0.0715	0.6395	-0.1735	0.1066
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	-0.0084	0.0715	0.9068	-0.1484	0.1317
personal_influence	0.0477	0.089	0.5920	-0.1267	0.2221
performance_achievement	0.0655	0.0692	0.3444	-0.0702	0.2012
cooperation_relationships	0.203	0.0844	0.0161	0.0376	0.3683
family_responsibility	0.257	0.0758	0.0007	0.1085	0.4056
processing_decisions	0.0645	0.0995	0.5171	-0.1306	0.2596
Group Var	1.038	0.1558	2.632e-11	0.7331	1.344

Dimension: efficiency

LMM (random intercept) — n = 717 ratings (239 participants)

Formula: efficiency ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	1.774	0.4951	0.0003	0.8039	2.745
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-1.049	0.1413	1.129e-13	-1.326	-0.7719
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	-0.0165	0.1568	0.9161	-0.3238	0.2908
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.1946	0.1562	0.2127	-0.5006	0.1115
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	0.0795	0.0697	0.2538	-0.057	0.216
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	0.0962	0.0697	0.1672	-0.0403	0.2328
personal_influence	-0.0799	0.0938	0.3946	-0.2638	0.104
performance_achievement	0.0582	0.073	0.4250	-0.0848	0.2013
cooperation_relationships	0.1788	0.0889	0.0444	0.0045	0.3532
family_responsibility	0.2113	0.0799	0.0082	0.0547	0.3678
processing_decisions	0.1606	0.1049	0.1259	-0.0451	0.3663
Group Var	1.271	0.1822	3.028e-12	0.9141	1.628

Dimension: understandability

LMM (random intercept) — $n = 717$ ratings (239 participants)

Formula: understandability ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	1.5	0.4623	0.0012	0.5939	2.406
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-0.6676	0.132	4.241e-07	-0.9262	-0.4089
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	0.0751	0.1465	0.6083	-0.2121	0.3622
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.0047	0.1459	0.9741	-0.2907	0.2812
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	0.0795	0.0588	0.1763	-0.0357	0.1947
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	0.0418	0.0588	0.4766	-0.0734	0.1571
personal_influence	-0.011	0.0877	0.9001	-0.1828	0.1608
performance_achievement	0.1183	0.0682	0.0829	-0.0154	0.252
cooperation_relationships	0.1759	0.0831	0.0343	0.013	0.3387
family_responsibility	0.0932	0.0746	0.2121	-0.0532	0.2395
processing_decisions	0.2054	0.0981	0.0362	0.0132	0.3975
Group Var	1.634	0.2234	2.601e-13	1.196	2.072

Dimension: manipulation

LMM (random intercept) — $n = 717$ ratings (239 participants)

Formula: manipulation ~ C(culture_group) + personal_influence + performance_achievement + cooperation_relationships + family_responsibility + processing_decisions + C(variant_name) + C(task_id)

term	estimate	se	p	ci_low	ci_high
Intercept	2.078	0.5541	0.0002	0.9918	3.164
C(culture_group)[T.European]	-1.162	0.1583	2.147e-13	-1.472	-0.8514
C(variant_name)[T.Commitment]	-0.0701	0.1757	0.6900	-0.4144	0.2742
C(variant_name)[T.Social Proof]	-0.0942	0.175	0.5902	-0.4371	0.2487
C(task_id)[T.t2_everyday_healthy]	-0.0042	0.0651	0.9488	-0.1318	0.1234
C(task_id)[T.t3_eco_friendly]	0.0293	0.0651	0.6529	-0.0983	0.1569
personal_influence	-0.0725	0.1051	0.4904	-0.2785	0.1335
performance_achievement	0.3169	0.0818	0.0001	0.1566	0.4772
cooperation_relationships	-0.0122	0.0997	0.9024	-0.2075	0.1831
family_responsibility	0.0258	0.0895	0.7735	-0.1497	0.2012
processing_decisions	0.0686	0.1176	0.5594	-0.1618	0.2991
Group Var	1.972	0.2619	4.973e-14	1.459	2.486

Appendix 6- RQ3: Strategy Effectiveness

6.1 Omnibus Wald Chi-Square Tests

Outcome	Variant χ^2	df	p(FDR)	Variant×Culture χ^2	df	p(FDR)	Variant×CogStyle χ^2	df	p(FDR)
chose_recommended	0.314	2	.858	1.596	2	.844	11.880	8	.422
picked_healthiest	1.739	2	.606	0.273	2	.934	14.798	8	.422
picked_most_sustainable	2.323	2	.606	2.734	2	.844	10.148	8	.548
chosen_health_score	3.090	2	.606	0.135	2	.934	6.406	8	.686
chosen_sustainability_score	0.707	2	.858	1.332	2	.844	5.525	8	.686

6.2 Descriptive Means by Explanation Strategy and Culture

Variant	Culture	Chosen Rec.	Picked Healthiest	Picked Most Sust.	Health Score	Sust. Score
Authority	Asian	0.410	0.385	0.658	68.26	91.37
Commitment	Asian	0.514	0.352	0.686	68.98	92.80
Social Proof	Asian	0.465	0.354	0.707	69.30	91.36
Authority	European	0.349	0.357	0.603	70.23	87.75
Commitment	European	0.384	0.312	0.601	70.87	89.29
Social Proof	European	0.303	0.379	0.576	72.21	86.21